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Abstract

This deliverable analyzes software practices within the five EOSC science clusters—PaNOSC, SSHOC, ESCAPE, ENVRI, and EOSC Life—via their software pilots. It evaluates software quality, developer acknowledgment, and community-oriented methods based on contributions from cluster representatives. The research underscores common strengths, including FAIR compliance, open-source development, and quality assurance tools, as well as problems such as uneven training resources, dependence on temporary personnel, and inadequate sustainability strategies. EVERSE can mitigate these deficiencies by fostering cross-cluster collaboration, hence advancing more standardized and sustainable software methods.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable analyses the practices of the five EOSC science clusters—**PaNOSC, SSHOC, ESCAPE, ENVRI, and EOSC Life**—through their software pilots to evaluate software quality and recognize the contributions of developers. The objective is to document community-driven metrics, tools, and strategies while identifying commonalities, differences, and gaps to inform future improvements.

The analysis is based on structured questionnaires and presentations provided by representatives of each cluster. Their inputs covered a range of topics, including software lifecycle management, sustainability plans, FAIR compliance, training resources, and recognition mechanisms. It's important to note that these inputs reflect the practices of specific organizations representing the clusters in EVERSE and may not capture the full scope of cluster-wide activities.

The analysis reveals several shared strengths across clusters, such as the widespread adoption of FAIR principles, open-source practices, and community-driven maintenance. Clusters utilize robust tools, including CI/CD pipelines and performance profilers, to ensure software quality. Training opportunities, such as workshops and tutorials, are widely available, though their standardization varies. Recognition mechanisms remain largely informal, relying on authorship in publications and repositories, with few structured incentive systems in place. Recurring gaps include the lack of standardized training resources, heavy dependence on temporary project-based developers rather than permanent staff, limited long-term sustainability strategies, and inconsistent recognition frameworks.

EVERSE is well-positioned to address the identified challenges through its cross-cluster collaboration framework.

1 Introduction

The EVERSE project aims to establish a framework for research software excellence, collaboratively designed and championed by research communities from five EOSC Science Clusters and national Research Software Expertise Centres. The project aims to build a European network for research software quality while laying the groundwork for a future Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence.

EVERSE Work Package 4 (WP4) serves as the interface of EVERSE to and from the EOSC science clusters. As a starting point, Deliverable 4.1 collects well-established practices on software engineering processes, training, and recognition mechanisms from the various science domains. These insights will be combined with the work on metrics from WP2 and tools from WP3 to establish a software assessment process that can be piloted and adapted to the needs of the science clusters.

Specifically, the deliverable documents the metrics, tools, and practices used across science clusters to evaluate software quality and recognize developers' contributions. Through an analysis of pilot software used by the five science clusters—**PaNOSC**, **SSHOC**, **ESCAPE**, **ENVRI**, and **EOSC Life**—we identify commonalities, differences, and gaps in current practices, providing a foundation for collaborative improvements.

The input for this deliverable was collected through a combination of structured questionnaires and presentations from representatives of the clusters, who provided insights into their organization's practices on software quality evaluation, sustainability strategies, training resources, and recognition mechanisms.

The information provided reflects the diverse nature of these communities. Some representatives focused on specific software tools within their organizations, while others provided broader overviews of practices and tools. While this variability limits how widely we can generalize the findings across entire clusters, it offers valuable insights into concrete, real-world approaches. Table 1 describes the domains represented by the science clusters and their corresponding organizations in EVERSE.

Table 1: EOSC Science Clusters represented in EVERSE

Cluster	Description	Organization in EVERSE
PaNOSC	Focuses on photon and neutron science, enabling advanced experiments through robust software tools	Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR)
SSHOC	Serves the social sciences and humanities, addressing unique challenges in linguistic, historical, and societal data	Lindat/CLARIAH-CZ (Charles University)
ESCAPE	Supports astronomy and particle physics by providing cutting-edge frameworks for data processing, reconstruction and data analysis for experiments.	University of Manchester

ENVRI	Serves as essential facilities for providing data, research products, and services across the four subdomains of Earth system science: Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth, and Biodiversity/Terrestrial Ecosystems.	University of Amsterdam
EOSC Life	Facilitates life sciences research, with an emphasis on workflow reproducibility and cross-discipline collaboration	ELIXIR

The deliverable complements other EVERSE initiatives, particularly WP2 (D2.1), which evaluates additional software quality metrics, WP3 (D3.1), which will provide an initial catalogue of RSQKit Tools for Assessing and Improving Software Quality and FAIRness, and WP5 (D5.1), which outlines a roadmap for software sustainability, quality, and recognition. Combined with WP4's work, these efforts form a comprehensive strategy to address software challenges and advance open science practices.

2 Methodology

This deliverable employs a systematic approach to analyse software quality practices and recognition mechanisms across the five EOSC science clusters. Our methodology combines qualitative and quantitative data collection through two primary instruments:

1. **Structured Questionnaires:** Representative developers of pilot software from **PaNOSC, SSHOC, ESCAPE, ENVRI, and EOSC Life** were asked to complete detailed questionnaires designed to capture specific metrics, tools, and practices related to software development, maintenance, and recognition systems.
2. **Expert Seminars:** Each cluster representative delivered a comprehensive seminar to WP4 partners containing the answers from the questionnaires, providing in-depth insights into their institutional practices, challenges, and success stories in software quality management and sustainability initiatives.

The following subsections outline our questionnaire structure and data analysis approach.

2.1 Questionnaire Structure

The questionnaire was organized into eight main categories to examine different aspects of software practices across the clusters:

1. **Communities of Software Developers and Users:** Identifying who develops and uses the software and assessing their levels of expertise.
2. **Technical Aspects:** Exploring software tiers, technical specifications, and deployment environments.
3. **Software Lifecycle:** Understanding version control practices, contribution policies, and developer/user onboarding processes.
4. **Metrics and Tools:** Identifying quality indicators and tools used to evaluate software performance and maintainability.
5. **FAIR Principles:** Evaluating the adherence to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, including repository use and citation practices.
6. **Sustainability Plans:** Examining management strategies, funding sources, and community contributions to sustain software development.
7. **Training Resources:** Identifying existing training platforms, workshops, and resources for software development and usage.
8. **Recognition Mechanisms:** Understanding how software developers are rewarded within the community.

2.2 Data Organization and Analysis

The data collected from the presentations and questionnaire responses were compiled into a comprehensive spreadsheet. This spreadsheet was structured to align responses by cluster, with separate columns for each software example or general overview provided:

- **Single software examples** (e.g., SSHOC) were documented in one column.
- **Multiple software cases** (e.g., PaNOSC, ESCAPE, ENVRI) were entered into separate columns to maintain clarity.
- **General organizational overviews** (e.g., EOSC Life) were summarized in one column.

Detailed responses from the questionnaires are provided in the Appendices.

The responses were then analysed to identify commonalities, domain-specific approaches, and gaps in current practices. This analysis forms the basis of the subsequent chapters, where each question is addressed in detail, supported by specific examples and comparative insights.

3 Communities of Software Developers and Users

The effectiveness, quality, and long-term sustainability of research software depend heavily on the communities that develop and maintain it, as well as those who utilize it. This chapter presents a comprehensive analysis of developer and user ecosystems across the five science clusters, drawing insights from their responses to our questionnaire. We examine the composition, expertise levels, and interaction patterns within these communities to identify best practices and areas for improvement.

3.1 Developer Communities

The developer communities across the science clusters vary widely in size, organization, and expertise. Most clusters rely on a mix of institutional support, small core teams, and contributions from early-career researchers (ECRs). Below is a summary of the key characteristics:

- **Small Teams with Institutional Support:** Some software projects, such as **PIConGPU** (PaNOSC) and **UDPipe** (SSHOC), are developed by small teams within research institutions. These teams include domain specialists and often also include computer scientists. For example:
 - **PaNOSC (PIConGPU):** Developed at HZDR by a team of computer scientists and physicists, the project is primarily driven by Ph.D. and master's thesis work.
 - **SSHOC (UDPipe):** Led by a single assistant professor at Charles University, with occasional contributions from students as part of academic projects.
 - **xAODAnaHelpers (ESCAPE):** Developed and maintained by a small team of ECRs, with a user base of physicists that makes contributions wherever their use case requires.
 - **ENVRI Knowledge base and LifeWatch VRE (ENVRI):** developed and maintained by researchers from UvA and LifeWatch Virtuan Lab Innovation Center (VLIC). LifeWatch is a RI in ENVRI. Key algorithms in the Knowledge base (e.g., for search, and recommendation) and in the VRE (e.g., for workflow scheduling and optimization), are the results of PhD work.
- **Short-Term Contributors:** Some clusters rely heavily on short-term contributors, such as interns, students, and postdocs, for software development. While this brings fresh ideas, it challenges long-term sustainability. For example:
 - **ESCAPE (BALER):** Ph.D. candidates and postdocs oversee development by summer students and interns.
 - **ENVRI Hub and its Components:** ENVRI Hub components are being developed by different teams, which consist of Research Software Engineers (RSEs) from different Research Infrastructures and community contributors, often supported by rolling institutional projects.
- **Collaborative Teams:** Some clusters operate with organized collaborative teams. For instance:
 - **ESCAPE (ACTS):** A team of physicists and computer scientists at CERN and worldwide leads development, integrating independent contributions into the core project.
 - **EOSC Life (Workflow Hub):** Domain specialists and software engineers collaborate on tool creation and maintenance.

3.2 User Communities

The user communities across the clusters are diverse, encompassing a wide range of expertise, disciplines, and needs. This diversity directly influences how the software is designed and made usable. We observe three main categories of users:

- **Domain-Specific Experts:** Some software tools are designed for advanced users with deep domain knowledge. For example:
 - **PaNOSC (PIConGPU):** Used by advanced C++ programmers for simulating laser-driven particle acceleration.
 - **ESCAPE (ACTS):** Used by physicists involved in high-energy physics experiments at the Large Hadron Collider that perform low-level particle reconstruction (prior to the final data analysis).
- **Multidisciplinary and Diverse Users:** Some software supports a broader audience, including users from multiple disciplines and varying technical expertise:
 - **SSHOC (UDPipe):** Serves a diverse user base ranging from non-technical users who can access pre-trained Natural Language Programming (NLP) models through a web interface, to computational linguists who train new models.
 - **ENVRI Hub / Virtual research Environment:** Serves junior researchers, environmental scientists, and developers creating research workflows.
 - **EOSC Life (Workflow Hub):** Serves life science researchers with tools for creating reproducible and shareable research workflows.
- **Non-Technical Users:** Some tools prioritize accessibility for users with limited technical skills through user-friendly interfaces and comprehensive documentation:
 - **SSHOC (UDPipe):** Provides web-based forms, detailed tutorials, and third-party integrations for non-programmers.
 - **ENVRI Hub / Notebooks:** Provides Jupyter-based workflows with integrated code and documentation to streamline research workflows.

3.3 Challenges and Opportunities

Science clusters face two main challenges: their dependence on short-term contributors, which affects software continuity, and the need to balance advanced functionality with accessibility for diverse users. Collaborative frameworks like those implemented in ESCAPE and EOSC Life can be considered as examples of sustainable approaches through a distributed network of developers sharing knowledge. Expanding training resources and improving onboarding processes can further enhance user engagement and support long-term development.

4 Technical Aspects

This chapter examines the software tiers and technical specifications across clusters, providing specific examples from each one.

4.1 Software Tiers

- **Tier 1 - Analysis Code:** Research software that implements computational methods for simulation, data processing, analysis and visualization.
- **Tier 2 - Prototype Tools:** Research software that tests new ideas or methods, typically as proof-of-concept implementations that can be used by others beyond the original project.
- **Tier 3 - Research Software Infrastructure:** Research software that implements established methods and models, requiring ongoing researcher collaboration for development.

4.2 Key Technical Specifications

Common technical specifications across clusters include:

- **Programming Languages:** Most software is written in **C++** or **Python**, often with language bindings to enable easy integration.
- **Execution Environments:** Software typically runs on **HPC systems**, **Virtual Research Environments (VREs)**, or cloud/distributed computing platforms.

4.3 Case Studies

Below are brief descriptions of one software example from each cluster, highlighting its tier and technical aspects:

1. **PaNOSC (PConGPU):**
 - **Tier 3** (Research Software Infrastructure).
 - **Technical Specifications:** Written in Modern C++ (C++17), with approximately 70,000 lines of code. Runs on HPC systems with complex CI pipelines for testing and validation.
2. **SSHOC (UDPipe):**
 - **Tier 2** (Prototype Tools) / **Tier 3** (Service).
 - **Technical Specifications:** Developed in C++ with Python bindings, ~50,000 lines of code. Runs on CPU/GPU systems and supports large-scale NLP tasks via REST services.
3. **ESCAPE (ACTS):**
 - **Tier 3** (Research Software Infrastructure).
 - **Technical Specifications:** Written in Modern C++, ~420,000 lines of code. It is used by High Energy Physics (HEP) experiments at CERN and runs on a range of platforms, including distributed computing through the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid.
4. **ENVRI (Notebook as a VRE System, and ENVRI -HUB):**
 - **Tier 3** (Research Software Infrastructure).

- **Technical Specifications:** Built in Python, integrated with Jupyter notebooks. Runs on Kubernetes-based cloud platforms and targets environmental science workflows.
5. **EOSC Life (Workflow Hub):**
- **Tier:** Tier 3 (Research Software Infrastructure).
 - **Technical Specifications:** Python-based infrastructure supporting tools like Galaxy, CWL, and Nextflow. Runs on cloud and VRE environments with a focus on reproducibility.

4.4 Challenges and opportunities

The clusters share commonalities such as use of modern programming languages like C++ and Python, reliance on HPC systems and cloud platforms for scalability, and integration of CI/CD pipelines.

However, they face challenges in maintaining performance and portability across diverse execution environments and addressing the high computational costs of complex Tier 3 workflows.

The technical aspects of the software across clusters demonstrate a strong focus on high-performance computing, modularity, and integration. While there are clear advancements in leveraging HPC and cloud environments, ensuring sustainability and addressing computational challenges remain ongoing priorities.

Additionally, a significant challenge faced across clusters is the workforce issue. Many clusters rely heavily on short-term contributors such as students, interns, and postdoctoral researchers for software development, which affects long-term sustainability and knowledge retention. The limited availability of permanent Research Software Engineers (RSEs) and structured career paths for software developers in research settings further exacerbates this issue. Addressing workforce challenges through structured training, recognition, and sustainable funding models is critical to ensuring long-term software development and maintenance.

EVERSE is specifically contributing to addressing this challenge through WP5, focusing on workforce sustainability by providing structured training and recognition mechanisms to support long-term engagement and retention in the research software ecosystem.

5 Software Lifecycle and Sustainability

This chapter explores how science clusters manage their software throughout its lifecycle, examining their version control practices, contribution policies, onboarding methods, and sustainability plans.

5.1 Lifecycle Management

Most clusters follow well-defined development workflows that include version control systems, contribution policies, and user onboarding. These practices ensure the software remains functional, maintainable, and adaptable over time.

- **Version Control and Contribution Policies:** All clusters use **Git-based platforms**, such as GitHub or GitLab, to manage version control and contributions. Common practices include:
 - Clear guidelines for contributions (e.g., pull requests and semantic versioning).
 - Use of CI/CD pipelines to validate changes and maintain quality.
 - Documentation hosted alongside the repositories (e.g. [readthedocs](#)) for transparency and ease of use.
- **Onboarding Practices:** Onboarding processes vary but often include:
 - **Workshops and tutorials** to introduce new users and developers.
 - **Mentoring programs** led by senior developers or researchers.
 - Use of example scripts and user stories to demonstrate real-world applications of the software.
 - As examples of onboarding practices:
 - **ESCAPE (ACTS)** conducts annual developer workshops with hands-on tutorials.
 - **PaNOSC (PIconGPU)** provides onboarding materials like videos, documents, and personal exchanges with core team members.

5.2 Sustainability Plans

The science clusters have developed strategies to ensure their software tools remain viable and effective over time, balancing financial resources with community engagement.

Funding Models:

Most clusters rely on institutional funding or project-based grants, for example:

- **PaNOSC and SSHOC:** Sustainability is supported by base funding from their host institutions (e.g., Helmholtz Center, Charles University).
- **ENVRI and EOSC Life:** Key software tools are integrated into larger infrastructures like LifeWatch ERIC, ensuring ongoing support through community contributors and follow-up projects.
- **ESCAPE (BALER):** The project receives short-term funding through specialized grants that focus on specific improvements to the software, for example to facilitate interdisciplinary use or to improve environmental sustainability.

Community-Driven Maintenance:

Several clusters adopt community-based maintenance models, where users help maintain the software they rely on:

- **SSHOC (UDPipe):** Maintained by the lead developer with occasional support from students and collaborators.

- **ESCAPE (ACTS, xAODAnaHelpers):** Contributions from short-term collaborators are integrated into the main repository by a core development team.
- **ENVRI Hub Components:** Maintained by a mix of Research Software Engineers (RSEs) and community contributors.

5.3 Challenges and Opportunities

All clusters excel in version control through Git-based platforms with CI/CD pipelines and provide comprehensive onboarding through workshops, tutorials, and documentation. However, they also face significant obstacles. These include a heavy reliance on short-term contributors (leading to expertise gaps), limited stable funding for long-term development, and difficulties in transitioning research prototypes to production infrastructure. Community contributions and institutional support help maintain the software, but expanding funding models and strengthening community involvement will be crucial for ensuring long-term sustainability and success of these software ecosystems.

6 Metrics and Tools for Evaluating Technical Quality

Evaluating the technical quality of research software is essential for ensuring its reliability, maintainability, and performance. This chapter examines the approach taken by science clusters to assess and maintain software quality. Across all clusters, there is a strong emphasis on maintainability and performance evaluation, supported by robust continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) pipelines alongside automated testing procedures. To achieve high reliability and efficiency standards, the clusters have adopted static code analysis tools and performance profilers (see below) as integral components of their quality assurance processes.

To monitor and improve quality, the clusters rely on a variety of tools and practices:

- **Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD):**
 - Automated testing frameworks integrated with Git-based platforms ensure code changes are validated before deployment.
 - Example: **PaNOSC (PIconGPU)** uses an extensive CI system to test code on multiple hardware configurations.
- **Static Code Analysis:**
 - Tools like **SonarCloud** are used to identify code issues, measure complexity, and improve maintainability.
 - Example: members of **ESCAPE** plan to use SonarCloud to provide insights into code quality and maintainability for the **ACTS** software
- **Performance Profiling:**
 - Tools such as NVIDIA Nsight, AMD Omnipperf, and Valgrind are used to monitor and optimize performance in resource-intensive applications on different platforms.
 - Example: **SSHOC (UDPipe)** tracks performance metrics to ensure the tool's efficiency in NLP tasks.
- **Code Coverage and Testing Tools:**
 - Testing frameworks and coverage analysis tools ensure thorough validation of software functionality.
 - Example: **EOSC Life (Workflow Hub)** includes CI pipelines with automated tests to validate workflows.

6.1 Challenges and Opportunities

While these tools and practices demonstrate a strong commitment to software quality, their implementation varies across clusters. Some focus on performance optimization, while others also prioritize code quality and maintainability. This diversity in approaches reflects the different requirements and priorities of each cluster's specific domain and use cases.

The primary challenges include implementing consistent quality metrics across diverse hardware environments, managing the varying approaches to software quality assessment, and ensuring comprehensive testing across different platforms. However, these challenges also present opportunities for advancement through the robust tooling ecosystem already in place, including CI/CD pipelines, sophisticated performance profiling tools, and modern development infrastructure utilizing containerization and microservices. The standardization of quality metrics and testing procedures across clusters could lead to improved

interoperability and more efficient resource utilization. Any standardisation must still consider the (domain-specific) characteristics of software used in different communities in each cluster, e.g. in terms of I/O needed for such tests and metric to be effective, but also in terms of developer expertise and availability for their implementation.

7 FAIR and Open Science Aspects of Software

Ensuring that research software aligns with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles and open science practices is critical for enabling collaboration, reproducibility, and long-term usability. This chapter examines how FAIR principles are implemented across the science clusters, focusing on repository use, licensing, citation mechanisms, and documentation practices.

7.1 FAIR Practices

The science clusters adopt various FAIR principles to make their software accessible and reusable:

- **Repository Use:** All clusters host their software on open repositories like GitHub or GitLab, ensuring public access to the source code.
 - Example: **PaNOSC (PICongPU)** and **ESCAPE (ACTS)** and **EOSC-Life (Workflow Hub)** pilots use GitHub for code hosting and collaboration.
- **Licensing:** Most clusters use open-source licenses such as **GPL**, **Apache 2.0**, or **MPLv2**, enabling reuse and adaptation.
 - Example: **SSHOC (UDPipe)** employs the Mozilla Public License (MPLv2) and provides clear licensing terms for linguistic models.
- **Citation Mechanisms:** Many tools are citable through DOI assignments, often via platforms like Zenodo, ensuring proper attribution.
 - Example: **EOSC Life (Workflow Hub)** links its software to publications and assigns DOIs for reproducibility.
- **Community Catalogues:** Some clusters maintain registries for community use, such as the ENVRI Training Hub or the SSHOC Marketplace.

7.2 Documentation Practices

Good documentation is essential for making software accessible to users and developers. Practices include:

- **Comprehensive Documentation:** Most clusters provide detailed user and developer guides, often hosted alongside the code repository.
 - Example: **ENVRI Hub Components** include documentation for Jupyter-based workflows, maintained by core developers.
- **Maintenance and Updates:** Documentation is usually updated as part of the development process or by core contributors.
 - Example: **PaNOSC (PICongPU)** maintains multiple levels of documentation (for users, developers, and maintainers) integrated with their CI pipelines.

7.3 Challenges and Opportunities

The clusters demonstrate strong adherence to FAIR principles through several key practices. Their open-source infrastructure includes publicly accessible repositories on platforms like GitHub, clear open-source licensing to ensure legal reusability, and Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) that enable proper citation.

Documentation practices are integrated into development workflows to promote consistency, with API documentation and user guides supporting implementation. Regular updates help maintain documentation relevance.

While these practices establish a solid foundation for open science, two main challenges persist: documentation quality varies across projects due to resource constraints, and limited standardization of community catalogues impacts software discoverability.

8 Training and Recognition

This chapter explores the training resources offered by the clusters and their methods for ensuring proper acknowledgment of contributors' work. This is only a selection of a broader list developed by EVERSE WP5.

8.1 Training Resources

The science clusters provide a range of training opportunities to support the development and use of research software:

- **Workshops and Dedicated Training:** The clusters organize comprehensive workshops and tutorials to train users and developers. Many participate in broader educational initiatives, including summer schools and training events. For example:
 - **ENVRI** offers training through its ENVRI Training Hub and LifeWatch ERIC Service Center
 - **ESCAPE** conducts hands-on tutorials during conferences and schools.
 - **PaNOSC** provides individualized onboarding processes for developers' skill building, along with basic training materials covering HPC, C++, etc.
- **Online Resources:** Clusters often provide online documentation, webinars, and example workflows to facilitate self-paced learning. For example:
 - **SSHOC (UDPipe)** includes detailed user documentation and manuals
 - **EOSC Life (Workflow Hub)** offers workflow-specific tutorials.

8.2 Recognition Mechanisms

Recognition practices vary across clusters, with some adopting formal systems while others rely on informal acknowledgments:

- **Authorship and Attribution:** Developers are often credited in software repositories and academic publications.
 - Example: **PaNOSC** lists contributors in software repositories, and **SSHOC** includes developers as co-authors in research papers.
- **Conference Opportunities:** Some clusters offer opportunities for developers to present their work at conferences.
 - Example: **ESCAPE** promotes developer visibility through conference talks and workshops, as well as encouraging citations of public material by developers through citation of technical papers and/or Zenodo repositories

8.3 Challenges and Opportunities

The science clusters have established a foundation of training and recognition practices through workshops, tutorials, and collaborative events, with contributions acknowledged primarily through academic authorship and repository credits. However, several challenges persist: training materials vary in quality and accessibility across clusters, beginner-friendly resources are limited, and recognition systems lack formal structure. There is a significant opportunity to strengthen community engagement and enhance software development ecosystems by establishing standardized training programs and creating more structured recognition systems that extend beyond traditional academic metrics.

9 Concluding Remarks

The five science clusters—PaNOSC, SSHOC, ESCAPE, ENVRI, and EOSC Life—demonstrate strong alignment in their adoption of open science principles, technical workflows, and community-driven practices. Open-source repositories, FAIR principles, and citation mechanisms like DOIs are universally embraced to ensure software accessibility and reusability. Most clusters rely on robust development workflows, including CI/CD pipelines and version control systems, to maintain software quality and usability. Collaborative training efforts, such as workshops and online tutorials, also play a central role in supporting both developers and users across the clusters.

Despite these shared strengths, the clusters exhibit notable differences shaped by their research domains and user communities. PaNOSC and ESCAPE primarily cater to specialized expert users in fields like high-energy physics, whereas SSHOC and ENVRI serve more diverse user bases, including non-experts. Similarly, sustainability strategies differ, with clusters like PaNOSC and SSHOC relying on institutional funding, while ENVRI and EOSC Life integrate their software into broader research infrastructures for long-term support.

Recurring gaps remain across the clusters, particularly in sustainability, training standardization, and developer recognition. Many clusters depend on short-term contributors, such as students and interns, which creates challenges in ensuring software continuity. Training resources, while available, often lack standardization and beginner-friendly materials, making onboarding more difficult for new users and developers. Recognition frameworks are largely informal, with limited financial rewards or career incentives, leaving contributions undervalued. Moreover, opportunities for cross-cluster collaboration are underutilized, limiting interoperability and knowledge exchange.

There are significant opportunities for collaboration and improvement. Developing standardized guidelines for training, sustainability, and software quality evaluation could address many of the existing gaps. Collaborative initiatives, such as cross-domain workshops and shared projects, could strengthen interoperability and foster knowledge-sharing among clusters. Establishing formalized recognition systems for developers, including financial incentives and career advancement pathways, would further enhance motivation and long-term engagement.

By addressing these gaps and leveraging shared strengths, the clusters can enhance their software ecosystems, improve sustainability, and advance research goals collectively.

Appendix I

Table 2. Questionnaire template

Questions
<p>(1) Describe the community that uses the software in your pilot -Who is the developer? (One, many, organised, less organised, changeable...) -Who are the users, and how experienced are they?</p>
<p>(2) Describe the technical aspects of the code in your pilot(s) according to the following template: -Software tier (Tier 1: Analysis code, Tier 2: Prototype Tools, Tier 3: Research Software Infrastructure (includes services)) -Technical specifications: language(s), size of codebase, where does it run (specify if it's on a VRE, HPC...)</p>
<p>(3) Describe your software lifecycle [https://zenodo.org/records/8324828] -This includes information in (1) but also the following points: --How has it been developed so far (version control, contribution policy) --How do you onboard new developers/users? -You can start by describing a “user story” (see page 4 of reference model)</p>
<p>(4) Are there indicators and tools applicable to your pilot(s) that provide insight into technical quality? -Do you or others in your community use them?</p>
<p>(5) Describe the FAIR / Open aspects of the code in your pilot(s): -See https://fair-software.eu/ for inspiration: are there a repository and a license, do you have a community registry/catalogue where the code is available, is it citable, do you have a “good software” checklist -How is the documentation maintained / by whom?</p>
<p>(6) Does your software have a sustainability plan? -This includes information on management, funding, contributors</p>
<p>(7) In your community, do you already have/know of training resources for developing/using software?</p>
<p>8) How are software developers rewarded in your community?</p>

Table 3: Responses: Cluster: PaNOSC / Organisation: HZDR / Software: PIconGPU and Alpaka.

PaNOSC/ HZDR/ PIconGPU	PaNOSC / HZDR /Alpaka
<p>Purpose: PIconGPU is a simulation code for laser induced plasma physics. It simulates how an ultrashort, extremely high energy pulse from a laser turns the matter it hits into plasma, which can in turn be use for laser wakefield acceleration of electrons and ions.</p> <p>Link: https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu</p> <p>Main related publication: https://doi.org/10.1145/2503210.2504564</p>	<p>Purpose: Alpaka is a header-only C++ template library that enables writing platform and performance portable applications. It can use CPUs with sequential and thread parallel code, GPUs via multiple programming paradigms and also FPGAs.</p> <p>Link: https://github.com/alpaka-group/alpaka</p> <p>Main related publication: https://doi.org/10.1109/IPDPSW.2016.50</p>
<p>Developers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mainly at HZDR • Team of (few) computer scientists and (more) physicists • Mainly driven through Ph.D./master thesis work <p>Users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mainly used for simulating laser driven particle acceleration • Advanced C++ users 	<p>Developers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jointly at HZDR and CERN (CMS) • Team of (few) computer scientists and (more) physicists • Mainly driven through Ph.D./master thesis work and CERN requirements <p>Users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced C++ users • HPC users hopping systems • CERN CMS experiment
<p>Software Tier Tier 3: Research Software Infrastructure (Services included)</p> <p>Technical Specs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Source: Modern C++17 ○ Python bindings available • Size of codebase: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~70 LOC (including PMacc library) ~30k comments + documentation • Where does it run: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Building and installation is via CMake ○ Ideally, can install on local machine if prerequisites are satisfied ○ Otherwise, any HPC systems ○ Very long compile times (~5+ minutes due to heavy templating) ○ Simulation parameters transported via CMake into code, needs recompile on input change 	<p>Software Tier Tier 3: Research Software Infrastructure (Services included)</p> <p>Technical Specs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Source: Modern C++17 • Size of codebase: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~90k LOC (50k headers) • Where does it run: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Code itself does “not run” ○ Header only library ○ Compiler will translate templates/structs/lambdas into native target code (CUDA, HIP/ROCm, OpenMP)
<p>How has it been developed so far?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Version control: Git – main code platform is GitHub • Contribution guidelines in CONTRIBUTING.md in the repo <p>How does it onboard new users?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online videos and onboarding documents • Mattermost team with core users <p>Personnel exchange visits</p>	

<p>Continuous Integration (CI) Very extensive and complex CI setup Moves code from GitHub via GitLab.com to HZDR local GitLab CI infrastructure Pushes all pipeline results back to GitHub PRs Checks both static code quality (linting, code style) Compiles test case for all supported combinations of hardware architectures, accelerators (GPUs), libraries > 1000s of CI jobs Runs tests and checks for completion and expected output</p> <p>Performance tools Code works fine with NVIDIA nsight, AMD Omnipperf, Score-P etc. Highly asynchronous nature makes profiling very hard</p> <p>Fun fact Code also part of mutiple HPC compiler and hardware vendor CI/CD-Test environments</p>	
<p>Repository: -PICongGPU – GitHub https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu)</p> <p>License: GPLv3+ (Libraries LGPLv3+, Documentation CC-BY 4.0)</p> <p>Citeable: yes (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.591746)</p> <p>Discussion Community: via GitHub Issues</p> <p>Software Quality Checklist: Commit Rules https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu/blob/dev/docs/COMMIT.md)</p> <p>Documentation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple levels of documentation (for users, developers, maintainers) • Mainly written and maintained by core dev team (or part of pull requests) • https://picongpu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/ 	<p>Repository: Alpaka – GitHub (https://github.com/alpaka-group/alpaka)</p> <p>License: MPLv2 (Documentation CC-BY 4.0)</p> <p>Citeable: yes (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.595380)</p> <p>Discussion Community: via GitHub Issues</p> <p>Software Quality Checklist: Coding Guidelines https://alpaka.readthedocs.io/en/latest/dev/style.html)</p> <p>Documentation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple levels of documentation (for users, developers, maintainers) • Mainly written and maintained by core dev team (or part of pull requests) • https://alpaka.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Part of Helmholtz base funded research activities • Permanently funded RSE as maintainer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Part of Helmholtz base funded research activities • Permanently funded RSE as maintainer
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project builds on well-established FOSS community practices • Onboarding of developers highly individual process (regarding skill building) • Basic training material for introduction to HPC, C++, C++ TMP, CMake, RSE development with GitHub/GitLab would be highly welcome 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Author / contributor list in software repo 	

- Software authors for specific scientific use case also listed in academic publications as authors

Table 4: Responses: Cluster: SSHOC / Organisation: LINDAT, CLARIAH-CZ / Software: UDPipe; Cluster: ESCAPE / Organisation: University of Manchester / Software: BALER.

SSHOC/ LINDAT / CLARIAH-CZ/UDPipe	ESCAPE / University of Manchester/BALER
<p>Purpose: UDPipe is a trainable pipeline for tokenization, tagging, lemmatization and dependency parsing of CoNLL-U files (format for text files used by e.g. linguists)</p> <p>Link: https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/udpipe/2</p> <p>Main related publication: https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/K17-3009</p>	<p>Purpose: software compressing scientific data using ML (autoencoder architecture) and providing performance metrics</p> <p>Link: https://github.com/baler-collaboration</p> <p>Main related publication: https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202429509023</p>
<p>Developers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single developer: assistant professor, originally a Natural Language Processing (NLP) • Cooperation with team providing the REST service infrastructure. <p>Users</p> <p>The user base is highly diverse with respect to background and technical expertise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Users that only want to use existing models but can and are willing to program. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ They are capable of calling a REST service or writing a simple program performing custom batch processing, etc. ○ Users that want to use the existing models without any programming –either through a web-based form, 3rd party integration or a binary they can download and then run. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The web-based form and good step-by-step documentation is important for them. ○ Integration into corpus management/creation tools (TEI: TOK) ○ Some users are NLP engineers/researchers that want to train the models; usually very knowledgeable. ○ Another group are computational linguists that want to develop treebanks (datasets showing links between words); therefore, they train new models, ideally using a provided binary without additional programming involved. ○ Companies providing NLP services for customers. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ These care a lot about resources requirements, performance, want bindings to various languages/pipelines. 	<p>Developers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mainly Early Career Researchers. Most development done by summer students (GSoC), interns, master’s students, PhD students. • High engagement of developers, but short term (weeks-months for students/interns) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Often very limited prior ML, particle physics experience ○ Managed by PhDs, postdocs (weekly meetings) <p>Users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Often users and developers coincide • Multi-discipline. So far, collider particle physics, other particle physics, computational fluid dynamics, astrophysics, industry • Designed to be easy to use out of the box, and can be developed further (e.g. implement new models or benchmarking tools) with some ML and Python knowledge
<p>Software tier</p> <p>Tier 2 - prototype (UDPipe 2)/service (UDPipe 1)</p>	<p>Software Tier</p> <p>Tier 2 - Prototype tools</p>
<p>Technical Specs</p>	

<p>The prototype:</p> <p>~642 models (74 languages)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CPU-only and also GPU-based models ○ Versioned in git vcs (currently hosted on github, 363 stars) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1st commit on Github in Feb 2016 ○ 601 commmits to v1 branch (~50k LOC C/C++) ○ 192 commits to v2 branch (since Aug 2020; ~2.5k LOC python) <p>The service:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ the service uses 5 GPUs with ~90GB RAM; runs on prem in several LXC containers in Proxmox VE ○ in 2023 ~ 90k requests/day (32 343 865 / year) 	<p>Technical Specs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Built on industry standard implementations (PyTorch). ● Runs on CPU, GPU or dedicated hardware (FPGA, and anything supported by PyTorch). ● Docker to allow easy use of batch computing / VRE. ● Can run on laptop up to HPC. <p>Code: Python, hosted on [GitHub], ~400MB including datasets and examples</p>
<p>How has it been developed so far?</p> <p>UDPipe was from the beginning created as a project to perform morphosyntactic analysis using data from the UD project, with the goal of being available as a service. It was developed by a main developer, who collaborated with an infrastructure team providing the resources for the service. The initial prototype was based on in-house existing tools and prototypes. The initial set of models was described in a research paper, the software released in source/binary (Github releases, PyPI, CPAN)/service, the tool documented. The source is developed in a Github repository under an MPL 2.0 license.</p> <p>Given that the tool allows training models and requires them for prediction, we have two kinds of lifecycles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lifecycle of the UD models ○ Lifecycle of the tool itself <p>We provide basic support through Github issues. We react to bugs/problems in code; we do not guarantee to provide user-support per se.</p> <p>We are currently working on a continuation project/infrastructure that will host UDPipe 3 models. For this continuation project, some components are developed by the university students as part of their individual software project. The process then follows the university regulations; later, the result is integrated by the main maintainer.</p> <p>Lifecycle of the Models:</p> <p>The UD data are released twice year, the UD models usually yearly. Therefore, the lifecycle of the models is: \</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ select the target UD release ○ train the models 	<p>How has it been developed so far?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Developed on GitHub with version control ○ Public contributions welcome ○ All contributions reviewed in pull requests <p>How do you onboard new contributors?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Contributors are independent researchers with associated UG/master’s students ○ Contributors are distributed in different institutes ○ At this early stage, users are generally also contributors as they implement features that are needed by their use case ○ Tutorials for all levels of new users / contributors available ○ Improvements in progress ○ Users can also try out an early version of Baler (notebook-based) on the ESCAPE Virtual Research Environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Will be updated as part of EVERSE

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ evaluate the quality of the trained models (quantitatively) ○ test the models in the service ○ release the models <p>Lifecycle of the Tool: We have had releases of UDPipe 1.0, 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, and releases of UDPipe 2.0, 2.1 (semver).</p> <p>We start by formulating a goal, according to users' demand or running projects, and then follow a standard development cycle (one developer working on its own).</p> <p>The quality of the implementation is measured by the performance of the trained models (in terms of both accuracy and runtime/memory requirements).</p>	
<p>Code/performance checking</p> <p>UDPipe performs morphosyntactic analysis. We therefore have several possible measures of quality:</p> <p>The quality of the trained models (not pertaining to EVERSE). Such a quality can be quantitatively measured using standardized metrics and is reported for every released model. Performance on a dataset heavily used in the (NLP) community</p> <p>The performance of the implementation (training and inference computational and memory requirements, throughput in wps). Such evaluations can be published, but are very HW specific, and we usually do not publish them.</p> <p>The quality of the implementation. We measure this quality only indirectly, via the problems encountered when hosting the rest service (in the past years, there have been a few crashes caused by lack of memory, but nothing else) and reported by the users on the Github issues.</p> <p>Some projects in the community might have automated testing (run via GitHub actions).</p> <p>Some GitHub integrations (codacy, codeclimate,) are used as initial measure of code quality.</p>	<p>Code/performance checking</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Continuous integration performs industry-standard syntax checking (Black), and tests code remains functional ○ Pull requests must pass CI tests and syntax/code quality rules ○ Docker container built only if syntax/code quality rules satisfied (badge on repository)
<p>Code repository https://github.com/ufal/udpipe webpage https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/udpipe</p> <p>License UDPipe is a free software distributed under the Mozilla Public License 2.0 and the linguistic models are free for non-commercial use and distributed under the CC BY-NC-SA license, although for some</p>	<p>Code repository</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Publicly available GitHub repo <p>License Apache 2.0 Licence, moved from previous MIT after discussion with industry partners</p> <p>Citations</p>

<p>models the original data used to create the model may impose additional licensing conditions.</p> <p>Community registries https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/, https://lindat.cz/repository, https://vlo.clarin.eu , https://switchboard.clarin.eu/tools, WebLicht, https://b2find.eudat.eu , PyPI (https://pypi.org/project/ufal.udpipe/), CRAN, CPAN, ...</p> <p>Citations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Handle (hdl) via https://lindat.cz/repository for models and sources ○ research publications (UDPipe 1 publications have ~1300 citations in Google Scholar; UDPipe 2 has ~300 citations) <p>Documentation Available at https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/udpipe/1, leading to subpages like https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/udpipe/1/install , https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/udpipe/1/users-manual , ... Documentation source is part of the repository https://github.com/ufal/udpipe/tree/master/doc Maintained by the main developer</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Citation via Zenodo in GitHub ● Major versions in Zenodo ● Currently missing good software checklist, but score very highly on FAIR software checklist (eScience Netherlands) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lose a little bit on version number structure and file formats (Baler output is a numpy array, bespoke to each model trained). <p>Documentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ README, more of a QuickStart guide
<p>Sustainability considerations</p> <p>The sustainability plan has three main components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Resources required for the service hosting. This component is the responsibility of the infrastructure team. ○ Maintaining the released versions of the software. Currently, the maintainer of the released versions is the main developer, given that the maintenance required only a manageable effort; a more detailed plan would be formulated if the required effort increased. ○ Developing better-quality models. Development might be considered part of sustainability in our field, given the fast progress of deep learning area; therefore, without development, the model performance would decrease compared to the up-to-date alternatives. The development plan includes tracking the progress in the area (to know when the existing models have improved sufficiently) and tracking projects that could provide funding for the development. Once the suitable conditions are met, the development cycle of a new major version would start. 	<p>Sustainability considerations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Managed by post-doc under the guidance of academic with permanent position ● Good but seasonal supply of UG students ● Limited funding to hire RSE/PhD/post-doc to substantially contribute to development ● Wishlist to maintain knowledge: All reports, theses, grant proposals, conference abstracts, etc currently shared to collaborators via google drive, but should be uploaded on Zenodo like the public documents and have a wiki page to collate links.
<p>Training / onboarding</p>	<p>Training / onboarding</p>

<p>For the tool itself: All developers so far were university employees/students of Computer Science; therefore, we did not use any specific training resources, assuming they already have most of the required skills.</p> <p>For using UDPipe 1 (where users are non-programmers), we have a custom documentation (given that it is a custom system) available on https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/udpipe/1</p> <p>Community resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Workshops, webinars, full courses, training modules, example notebooks... ○ https://www.sshopencloud.eu/training ○ https://www.clarin.eu/content/learning-hub 	<p>We suggest new members follow HEP Software Foundation basic and advanced training courses in python, C++, data science and machine learning (already in WP5 list)</p> <p>For this software project in particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ We have example scripts and tutorials to allow for quick onboarding of new students, but these need to be expanded and updated ○ Currently building a Wiki collating past reports, further reading, conference abstracts, etc.
<p>Recognition</p> <p>Publications in the respective field: research publications with quantitative and qualitative model evaluations</p> <p>Demo sessions on conferences</p> <p>Shared tasks participations</p> <p>Github (or other open-source community) visibility</p> <p>Funding awarded in competition</p>	<p>Recognition</p> <p>Small team independent from larger collaborations allows for many conference talk opportunities, offered to all members</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Talks at CHEP 2023 and ICHEP 2024 as well as national / ECR conferences <p>Small to medium grants allow for ECRs to get experience in writing and as co-PIs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● So far, obtained two “pump-prime” grants with ECRs as PIs from the University of Manchester for (a) packaging and releasing Baler (4 months of RSE time from the university pool) (b) environmental sustainability of Baler (12 months of RSE time at 0.5 FTE for benchmarking this and other projects) <p>Papers feature all collaborators in alphabetical order</p>

Table 5: Responses: Cluster: ESCAPE / Organisation: University of Manchester/ Software: xAODAnaHelpers and ACTS.

ESCAPE / University of Manchester/ xAODAnaHelpers	ESCAPE / University of Manchester/ ACTS
<p>Purpose: analyse high-level data (reconstructed particles) from the ATLAS detector at the Large Hadron Collider</p> <p>Link: https://github.com/UCATLAS/xAODAnaHelpers</p> <p>Main related publication: N/A, but software citeable on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/7335128</p>	<p>Purpose: reconstruct tracks of charged particles from particle collisions at high energy particle accelerators.</p> <p>Link: https://github.com/acts-project</p> <p>Main related publication: https://doi.org/10.1007/s41781-021-00078-8</p>
<p>Developers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two main developers • Other contributors are physicists from the ATLAS collaboration <p>Users Typically PhD students Highly experienced in their domain (physics), not necessarily as software engineers</p>	<p>Developers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Developed by a team of Physicists and Computer Scientists at CERN <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The collaboration has an organized core developer team ○ Benefits from multiple small-scale projects by independent groups that can be merged into the main repository <p>Users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Used mainly by high energy physics (HEP) experiments at the LHC (predominantly ATLAS) ○ Expert Physicists, Software Developers ○ Currently in the process of deploying ACTS into core ATLAS reconstruction software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Main repo: ACTS ()
<p>Software tier Tier 1 – analysis code</p> <p>Technical Specs Language: Mostly C++, with python3 for configuration and steering</p> <p>Size of codebase: 54,650 LOC</p> <p>Where does it run? On the CERN LHC Worldwide Computing Grid (WLCG), locally for tests and small jobs</p>	<p>Software tier Tier 3 – Research Software Infrastructure</p> <p>Technical Specs Language: Source: Modern C++, Python bindings available</p> <p>Size of codebase: ~420k LOC (LOC counter for github repos, https://ghloc.vercel.app/)</p> <p>Where does it run? On computing clusters at CERN and on the CERN LHC Worldwide Computing Grid (WLCG)</p> <p>Documentation on where to run https://acts.readthedocs.io/en/latest/getting_started.html provides recipes to run via:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ LCG release on CernVM File System (CVMFS), https://cernvm.cern.ch/fs/ ○ Docker images ○ Building and installation is via CMAKE ○ Ideally, can install on local machine if prerequisites are satisfied, but long list of dependencies and this does not usually occur due to the high throughput nature of the software

<p>How has it been developed so far?</p> <p>Initiated in 2015, 1 maintainer who stepped down in 2023, then 2 maintainers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Users submit Merge Requests on GitHub ○ Maintainers discuss, edit, accept MRs ○ Development Workflow section in docs <p>Onboarding of new developers/users</p> <p>2023 call for new maintainers submitted in various ATLAS mailing lists of user groups</p> <p>Users come to maintainers with MRs / issues, no active recruitment</p>	<p>How has it been developed so far?</p> <p>Version control:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Git ● Semantic Versioning (https://semver.org/spec/v2.0.0.html) used for public API ● Conventional Commits (https://www.conventionalcommits.org/en/v1.0.0/) used for PRs <p>Contribution guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Code guidelines (https://acts.readthedocs.io/en/latest/codeguide.html) <p>Onboarding of new developers/users</p> <p>The dev team hosts regular workshops (eg. ACTS Dev Workshop '22, https://indico.cern.ch/event/1184037/overview) that include hands-on tutorial sessions that explain different components of the toolkit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Basic installation and examples ■ Using 3rd party plugins ■ Integrating custom pieces of code on top of the core library etc. <p>For ACTS-ATLAS integration specifically</p> <p>Annual Dev Workshop (https://indico.cern.ch/event/1374927/overview)</p>
<p>Benchmarking / code quality tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Github CI/CD used to check installation / compilation ○ No other tools in frequent use (yet) ○ Interaction with ATLAS groups for code optimisation (SPOT) and user analysis (AMG) ○ But more focussed on performance rather than software quality 	<p>Benchmarking / code qualitytools</p> <p>Static analysis tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SonarCloud (https://www.sonarsource.com/products/sonarcloud/) ■ Cloud based ■ Provides varied insights on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Issues ● Complexity ● Maintainability etc ■ Plan to use on ACTS in the future <p>Profiling:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ gperftools (prof.) + pprof (viz.) ○ Valgrind - Mem profiling ○ NSight suite by NVIDIA <p>Codecov (https://app.codecov.io/gh/acts-project/acts): Test coverage</p>
<p>Repository:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● github <p>https://github.com/UCATLAS/xAODAnaHelpers</p> <p>License: Apache 2.0 Licence</p> <p>Citeable: DOI on zenodo</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Advertised on github and in docs ● No citations yet <p>Community registry / catalogue?</p> <p>No, Active mailing list mostly used for support</p> <p>Software Quality Checklist:</p>	<p>Repository: https://github.com/acts-project/acts/tree/main</p> <p>License: MPLv2</p> <p>Citeable: https://github.com/acts-project/acts/blob/main/CITATION.cff</p> <p>Discussion Community: https://github.com/acts-project/acts/discussions</p> <p>Software Quality Checklist: https://acts.readthedocs.io/en/latest/contribution/guide.html</p> <p>Documentation:</p>

<p>N/A</p> <p>Documentation:</p> <p>Docs created with doxygen, hosted by ReadTheDocs, maintained by repo maintainers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Written and maintained by core dev team ○ Checklist for writing new documentation: https://acts.readthedocs.io/en/latest/contribution/documentation_cheatsheet.html ○ Documentation can also be built locally
<p>Sustainability considerations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Contributors & maintainers are people with interest to keep the software alive (e.g. they use the software in their analysis, calibration work etc.) ○ Few external incentives, since ATLAS does not publish papers on individual frameworks 	<p>Sustainability considerations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The project is open-source and was initially based on the ATLAS tracking software ● The core team is predominantly based at CERN, with numerous other short-term collaborators all over the world
<p>Training resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hosted hands-on tutorial during 2024 ATLAS UK week ○ Instructions on GitLab (include links to more general tutorials, e.g. ATLAS Software Tutorials, etc) ○ Some (somewhat outdated) tutorials in the docs 	<p>Software Quality</p> <p>The project mostly follows the C++ Core Guidelines (https://isocpp.github.io/CppCoreGuidelines/CppCoreGuidelines), with chosen naming conventions and formatting guidelines listed in the contribution guidelines</p>
<p>Recognition</p> <p>ATLAS “OTP system”: service tasks (like software maintenance) reward OTP points, these points decide (among other factors) who gets selected to give conference talks</p>	<p>Recognition</p> <p>Contributors are added to the list of authors</p> <p>Significant scientific contribution can result in talks at conferences or the publication of research papers where due authorship is given to contributors</p>

Table 6: Responses: Cluster: ENVRI / Organisation: University of Amsterdam / Software: ENVRI Hub Component: Knowledge Base Search Engine Component and VRE environment and ENVRI Hub Component: Notebook as a VRE (NaaVRE).

ENVRI / University of Amsterdam/ ENVRI Hub Component: Knowledge Base Search Engine Component and VRE environment.	ENVRI / University of Amsterdam/ ENVRI Hub Component: Notebook as a VRE (NaaVRE) system.
<p>User of the ENVRI HUB: -Users of the ENVRI community -Users from EOSC -Any junior researcher from environmental-related-scientific domain</p> <p>Developers Research Software Developers who develop the ENVRI Hub framework, research engines Developer for the community, e.g for the Data Management services</p>	<p>User of the ENVRI HUB: -Users of the ENVRI community -Users from EOSC -Any junior researcher from environmental-related-scientific domain -User of the VRE --Im this case could be also developer who develops workflows --Researchers that they use workflows</p> <p>Developers Research Software Developers who develop the ENVRI Hub framework, research engines Developer for the community, e.g for the Data Management services</p>
<p>Software Tier TIER3</p> <p>Technical specification Written in Python Run on Cloud via K8S Developers: The UniAmsterdam Team (2 developers) and Lifewatch VLIC Team (3 developers)</p>	<p>Software Tier TIER3</p> <p>Technical specification TIER1 Written in Python/ R As a Notebook (in Jupyter) of Dock-based workflow (on K8S) Developers:domain specialist</p>
<p>Software lifecycle Version Control: Git Research Data Management Guidelines for research artifacts CI/CD (via Git action) Docker</p>	<p>Software lifecycle Version Control: Git Research Data Management Guidelines for research artifacts CI/CD (via Git action) Docker</p>
<p>Indicators and Tools: Git CI/CD using Git action to automate the pipeline Docker and K8S to mobilise the code and run them on the cloud (micro)Services and FaaS desing Pattern Agile practice (Git Issue) the profesional developers are use it, looser with the students Vulnerability Scanning & Dependancies update</p>	<p>Indicators and Tools: Git CI/CD using Git action to automate the pipeline Docker and K8S to mobilise the code and run them on the cloud (micro)Services and FaaS desing Pattern Agile practice (Git Issue) the profesional developers are use it, looser with the students Vulnerability Scanning & Dependancies update</p>
<p>Open-source aspects License: Gudilens from Uni and Lifewatch> licensing is mandatory, Apache is used but not exclusively Curation: Basic curation of the software by the students (comments, readme) Tutorial: Webpage of the software and hands-on tutorial</p>	<p>Open-source aspects License: Gudilens from Uni and Lifewatch> licensing is mandatory, Apache is used but not exclusively Curation: Basic curation of the software by the students (comments, readme) Tutorial: Webpage of the software and hands-on tutorial</p>

<p>Citable software through the paper Documentation maintained by the developers based on software changes and feedback from the users</p>	<p>Citable software through the paper Documentation maintained by the developers based on software changes and feedback from the users</p>
<p>Sustainability plan Via Lifewatch ERIC, valuable software will be sustained as service/tool in the research infrastructure Community contributors can continue to maintain or upgrade the software through the Liefewatch ERIC Continue the development and maintenance of research software by proposing follow-up research projects (thesis or grant)</p>	<p>Sustainability plan Via Lifewatch ERIC, valuable software will be sustained as service/tool in the research infrastructure Community contributors can continue to maintain or upgrade the software through the Liefewatch ERIC Continue the development and maintenance of research software by proposing follow-up research projects (thesis or grant)</p>
<p>Training Service in ENVRI-HUB: https://training.envri.eu ENVRI has a training catalogue: https://trainingcatalogue.envri.eu/ (missing the Quality aspect from the training) LifeWatch Service Center: training for the LifeWatch Community: https://www.lifewatch.eu/organisation-governance/service-centre/ Uni Manchester has a master program on Software Engineering: https://www.manchester.ac.uk/study/masters/courses/list/21577/msc-software-engineering/ Frequent tutorial sessions at conferences and summer schools (EGU, ENVRI, summer school etc)</p>	<p>Training Service in ENVRI-HUB: https://training.envri.eu ENVRI has a training catalogue: https://trainingcatalogue.envri.eu/ (missing the Quality aspect from the training) LifeWatch Service Center: training for the LifeWatch Community: https://www.lifewatch.eu/organisation-governance/service-centre/ Uni Manchester has a master program on Software Engineering: https://www.manchester.ac.uk/study/masters/courses/list/21577/msc-software-engineering/ Frequent tutorial sessions at conferences and summer schools (EGU, ENVRI, summer school etc)</p>
<p>Recognition We plan to integrate notebook quality indicator in the VRE before the user share it Waiting ideas from EVERSE</p>	<p>Recognition We plan to integrate notebook quality indicator in the VRE before the user share it Waiting ideas from EVERSE</p>

Table 7: Responses: Cluster: ENVRI / Organisation: University of Amsterdam / Software: ECV Workflows: ENVRI Hub: Essential Climate Variables Workflows; Responses: Cluster: EOSC Life / Organisation: ELIXIR / Software: Presented different elements/ components of Workflow Hub.

<p>ENVRI / University of Amsterdam/ ENVRI ECV Workflows: ENVRI Hub: Essential Climate Variables Workflows".</p>	<p>EOSC Life/ ELIXIR/ Presented different elements/ components of Workflow Hub: eg. Galaxy, RO-Crate, CWL, nextflow etc.</p>
<p>Users:</p> <p>User of the ENVRI HUB: -Users of the ENVRI community -Users from EOSC -Any junior researcher from environmental-related-scientific domain -User of the VRE --Im this case could be also developer who develops workflows --Researchers that they use workflows</p> <p>Developers: Research Software Developers who develop the ENVRI Hub framework, research engines Developer for the community, e.g for the Data Management services</p>	<p>Developers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - one main developer - some other more recent developers - small contributions from third parties <p>Users:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coincide with developers - Others from related collaborations (EOSC-ENTRUST, EJP-RD project) on trusted research environments
<p>Software tiers:</p> <p>TIER1</p> <p>Technical specifications:</p> <p>Written in Python/ R As a Notebook (in Jupyter) of Dock-based workflow (on K8S) Developers:domain specialist</p>	<p>Software tiers:</p> <p>TIER 3</p> <p>Technical specifications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language: Python, from 3.7 to 3.13. • Codebase: 15MB of files, 65 python files, 186 classes and around 1000 methods. • Where does it run? It has been designed to be run both on command line, VRE and HPC environments.
<p>How has it been developed so far?</p> <p>Version Control: Git Research Data Management Guidelines for research artifacts CI/CD (via Git action) Docker</p>	<p>How has it been developed so far?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The project is using a public git repository since the beginning, where we receive the issues opened by the users. We have a written contribution policy, but so far, we have received only minor contributions. <p>Onboarding of new developers/users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We have organized a couple of seminars in the past, but we are mainly onboarding new developers and user by the word of mouth and the research projects where WfExS-backend is growing and being used.
<p>Indicators and Tools</p> <p>Git CI/CD using Git action to automate the pipeline Docker and K8S to mobilise the code and run them on the cloud</p>	<p>Indicators and tools</p> <p>The developers use both local and GitHub-based CI workflows to check the correctness of code at different levels in different Python versions, as well</p>

<p>(micro)Services and FaaS desing Pattern Agile practice (Git Issue) the profesional developers are use it, looser with the students Vulnerability Scanning & Dependancies update</p>	<p>as compatibility of licences with the licences of WfExS-backend, the code be written conforming PEP8 style and checking whether some vulnerability is associated with the frozen versions of the dependencies for the different python versions tested, in order to propose an update of them. Tools being used for that are, among others, pre-commit, pylint, mypy, black and pip-audit.</p>
<p>FAIR/Open-source aspects License: Gudilens from Uni and Lifewatch> licensing is mandatory, Apache is used but not exclusively Curation: Basic curation of the software by the students (comments, readme) Tutorial: Webpage of the software and hands-on tutorial Citable software through the paper Documentation maintained by the developrs based on software changes and feedback from the users</p>	<p>FAIR/Open-source aspects All code is available as open-source Licensed usually with Apache DO have community registered catalogue (number of repos. e.g. workflow hub, bioconductor) Maintained usually by the developers The source code is available at https://github.com/inab/WfExS-backend , with Apache2 license. Each time a release is minted, a Docker software container image is deployed at GitHub, and the source code is published at Zenodo. The repository has a CITATION.cff file describing the software repository, which is kept updated, as it is trusted by Zenodo. The project has a separate branch for the source files of the documentation, which is compiled and exposed at https://wfexs-backend.readthedocs.io</p>
<p>Via Lifewathc ERIC, valuable software will be sustained as service/tool in the research infrastructure Community contributors can continue to maintain or upgrade the software through the Liefewatch ERIC Continue the development and maintenance of reasearch software by proposing follow-up research projects ()thesi or grant</p>	<p>Sustainability plan: Management: small groups or groups depending on the success of the software The list of contributors is partially maintained at CITATION.cff . We have documentation about how to contribute, as well as the code of conduct. But we have not explicitly described the funding.</p>
<p>Training Service in ENVRI-HUB: https://training.envri.eu ENVRI has a training catalogue: https://trainingcatalogue.envri.eu/ (missing the Quality aspect from the training) LifeWatch Service Center: training for the LifeWatch Community: https://www.lifewatch.eu/organisation-governance/service-centre/ Uni Manchester has a master program on Software Engineering: https://www.manchester.ac.uk/study/masters/courses/list/21577/msc-software-engineering/ Frequent tutorial sessions at conferences and summer schools (EGU, ENVRI, summer school etc)</p>	<p>Training resources We have some scarce, somewhat outdated materials about how to install the software and the first steps. We are going to centralize those materials in the official documentation hosted at https://wfexs-backend.readthedocs.io</p>
<p>Recognition</p>	<p>Recognition Try to give visibility to the contributos</p>

<p>We plan to integrate notebook quality indicator in the VRE before the user share it Waiting for feedback from EVERSE</p>	
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Appendix II: User story from EOSC-Life pilot

The typical user story of a WfExS-backend user is one where a researcher wants to execute a scientific workflow which can be later reproduced. Both the inputs and the workflow must be available through permanent identifiers which can be used by WfExS-backend in order to fetch them locally. The kind of scientific workflows recognized by WfExS-backend are the ones written either in CWL or Nextflow, preferably the ones whose steps are based on software containers. Once WfExS-backend has materialized the inputs, the workflow engine, the workflow and its dependencies, all the provenance needed to reproduce the analysis later has been gathered. As WfExS-backend prepares the execution scenario to allow it to be run in isolated environments, like HPC, it is recommended to use workflows which do not depend on or issue queries to web services. Once the execution has been performed, the provenance of the execution itself is also gathered, so the complete analysis can be described in a Workflow Run RO-Crate. Last, the user can choose to deposit or publish either the results or the RO-Crate itself into Zenodo, B2SHARE, Dataverse or a Nextcloud service, obtaining a permanent identifier in the process.